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Education Development Programming: Responsiveness and Adaptability of the Implementation of the Malawi National Reading Programme in Lungwena, Mangochi District

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Abstract

The study assessed the implementation of the Malawi nation reading Programme's theoretical grounding and its localisation based on context. The methodology included a standardised reading assessment that tested the ability of children to read and regressed contextual factors to examine how they contributed to the reading skills of pupils. Results showed that the programme was well grounded in theory but lacked awareness of the implementation context. Therefore, the study recommends a balance of effort and investment in the implementation of reading programmes for optimal and sustained reading skill gains by pupils.

Keywords: Reading, Planning, Education, Context

1. Introduction

The past two decades have seen a focus in education development programming on the teaching of reading. Reading has been rightly placed as a foundational skill required for learning (UNESCO, 2017). Like in many African countries, Malawi has had a fair share of experiences developing her reading programme that has fundamentals of the teaching of reading in design. The Malawi Reading Programme follows a phonics approach anchored by the 5 T's for effective reading instruction (Teaching, Time (Ministry of Education, 2016), Text (Anderson, R.C., Wilson, P.T., & Fielding, L.G., 1986), Tongue (Langer, 2010; Kachiwanda, 2010), Test). The phonics approach in Malawi has followed a transitional approach where students are taught to learn the letters, sound them, add them for syllables, use the syllables in familiar and non-familiar word reading, apply comprehension strategies, and qualify as readers above-set thresholds. The teaching instruction for respective grades is highly scripted and teachers implement it with fidelity across Primary Schools in Malawi.

Notwithstanding the insulated approach on the programming of the reading intervention in Malawi, its universalization, and other household factors found to influence the ability of children to read were not pre-

programmed to complement the approach stated above. It is unclear how policy decisions from the generated evidence inform collaborative learning and adaptability on the development and implementation of reading interventions.

Gaps in knowledge identified above were therefore examined in a reading assessment conducted in Mangochi District in Malawi that sought to understand the relationship between acquisition of reading skills and household factors that would further inform education development programming focus as it relates to the Malawi National Reading Programme and other programmes developed and implemented similarly in countries such as Ethiopia and Liberia (De Stefano, J., Slade, T., & Korda, M., 2013; Chiapetta, M., 2013; Piper B. , 2010).

2. The theoretical and empirical literature

Reading programme in Malawi has followed the universally proven efficient phonics approach (Roberts, 1994), (Richards, J.C and Willy A. Renandya, 2002), and (USAID, 2016). This has been complemented by the basic elements that support the delivery of a phonics-based reading approach focusing on teaching, time, text, tongue, and test (Gentaz, E., Sprenger, L & Theure A., 2015) and (Piper B. , 2010). However, the deployment of the phonics approach left out key elements that support learning of reading at the household level. Therefore, one cannot conclusively attach the magnitude of reading gains to the phonics approach alone.

Studies that have been conducted on effects of household factors on learning have identified language used at home (Nagarajan, Gonzalez & Hur, 2017) and (Harrington & Sawyer, 1992; Dickinson & McCabe, 2002), meals taken by pupils (Howard, 2010), time a learner is read to at home (Roundy and Roundy, 2009; Pang, Muaka, Bernhardt and Kamil, 2010; Mastropieli, Leinart and Scruggs, 1999; Denton, Anthony, Parker, and Hasbrouck, 2004) as among other factors that predict the ability of pupils to learn reading. While literature points to the complementarity of these factors, reading programmes implemented in the past two decades have largely focused investments and attention on phonics instruction as key in the learning of reading predictors are considered as leverage to reading skill gains in pupils as an approach leaving out focus on complementing factors. This withstanding, programming for the reading interventions has been cast on the phonics enablers, leaving out complementary factors to the phonics-led reading approach. Nonetheless, the programming of reading interventions does not invest in preconditions that sustain reading gains and increase the achievement margins, regardless of well-researched theoretical underpinnings guiding the development of reading programmes.

As for Malawi, the national reading programme implementation has followed a similar trend described above. This is where, evidence is generated on household enablers of learning reading, but investment decisions do not change in line with evidence (Nagarajan, Gonzalez & Hur, 2017).

In the absence of a case study on a combined investment that has tackled the underpinning theoretical approach in reading programmes together with investments in the complementary factors mentioned above, assessments have stopped at pointing to what factors makes a difference e.g. parent education (Zambrana, K. A., Hart, K. C., Maharaj, A., Cheatham-Johnson, R. J., & Waguespack, A., (2019)), home reading environment (Elsje van Bergen Titia van Zuijen Dorothy Bishop Peter F. de Jong, 2016) and parental status (Kaluge, Kustiani & Indawati, 2019). The granular details on these broader factors would present an opportunity for more focused attention and inclusion in programming reading interventions that are specific to the context, optimizes value for money on itemized factors that are bankable, and compliments traditionally thought process exhibited in the development of reading interventions.

3. Experimental/Materials and methods

To understand the relationship of household factors on the ability of pupils to learn reading and how such relationships could influence the programming of reading interventions, a reading test was conducted in 17 schools and reached out to 230 pupils in Mangochi District, Malawi. The test targeted 11-12-year-olds, assessing their ability to acquire reading skills for an equivalent of two years. Test items that the students were tested on included: 1) letter naming, 2) letter sounds, 3) Oral reading fluency (ORF), 4) comprehension and 5) extended

comprehension. Further data was collected from the students on the household factors that may have influenced their ability to acquire reading skills apart from enrolling into a homogenous National Reading Programme that is standardized and well-controlled for implementation variations. The factors that pupils provided data on included the following 1) pre-school attendance, 2) meals each pupil took a day, 3) language spoken at home, 4) school attendance, 5) reading partners, 6) reading at home, 7) reading practice, 8) reading homework, 9) nutrition access intensity, 10) other sources of textbooks, 11) supplementary reading materials and 12) places where pupils read. The results from the reading tests were marked for each response item. There was a limited variance between the mean scores on the items in the test. However, the spread of the response variables in the test items was not normally distributed. Therefore, the response items were centered and standardized through the residuals for the mean score (*z-scores*) to enable the attachment of predictors to an independent variable whose residuals were standardized for analysis. Therefore, the *z-scores* indexed all test items from the reading test to a 0-101 percentage point range so that analysis of variances with each household is tested for influencing variance on how well pupils acquired reading skills. This was done to verify that differences in the reading ability of students are genuinely explained by these household factors and the reason behind the variation is not opportune. Document analysis was done on key recommendations related to household factors made on the Malawi National Reading Programme to assess whether the recommendations meant to add value to the design and implementation of the programme were incorporated.

4 Discussion of results

The results are discussed at three levels. 1) Predictors of reading based on the teaching of reading through phonics, 2) The analysis of variance and definition of key variables that significantly explain variation in the reading ability of the pupils assessed and 3) secondary data analysis on decisions made on the Malawi Reading Intervention based on evidence generated from assessments on reading predictors other than the theory-based posits that fundamentally informs the architecture of the reading programme.

4.1 Association of pre-reading skills to reading fluency

The study examined the association between pupils' mastery of pre-reading skills and reading fluency. The purpose of the study was to determine whether pupils who had mastered the phonics-based reading instruction were better readers than those who had difficulties learning to read through the phonics-based instruction. The test was conducted through an analysis of variance from the reading scores in the pre-reading sub-tasks in the reading test and their association with oral reading fluency. The hypothesis tested to determine such an association was phrased as below:

H0 = Pre-reading skills do not predict the acquisition of reading skills and the ability to read early in life, and

H1 = Pre-reading skills predict the acquisition of reading skills and the ability to read early in life; H0 is the null hypothesis, and H1 is the alternate hypothesis.

The dependent variable in the hypothesis testing described above was the oral reading fluency as measured by the number of correct words read per minute. In contrast, the pre-reading skills scores of the pupils were the observable variables. The pre-reading skills or sub tasks in the reading test included letter knowledge, syllable reading, and familiar word reading. The analysis of variance showed that the statistical Fisher test was highly significant and the regression coefficients of the predictors were not equal to zero, indicating that there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis and that the study provides a rationale for doing so. This finding validated the alternate hypothesis that pre-reading skills predict the acquisition of reading fluency, hence mastery of phonics-based instruction had a positive effect on the ability of study participants to acquire reading skills. The results of the test are presented in Table 15 below.

Table 1: Phonics reading instruction hypothesis test results.

	Number of Observations	310		R-squared	0.9638
	Root MSE (Explain)	11.34		Adj-squared	0.9133
Source	Partial SS	df	MS	f	Prob>F

Model	443103.79	180	2461.688	19.09	0***
Familiar Word Read	81801.923	53	1543.432	11.97	0***
Syllable reading	27210.096	65	418.6169	3.25	0***
Letter Knowledge	19454.778	62	313.7867	2.43	0***

The results presented in Table 1 above led to the conclusion that familiar word reading knowledge, syllable reading, and letter knowledge accurately predicts oral reading fluency. Pupils with stronger pre-reading abilities read more words from a given paragraph than pupils with weaker pre-reading abilities. This finding is further supported by the F-Statistic ($p=0$) and the observed R-squared (0.9638), implying that the findings are reliable and not a false result of peculiarities in the data set. This finding confirms the importance of pre-reading skills in teaching reading through phonics instruction and predicts the fluency of pupils as noted by reading instruction theorists (Graaff et al., 2009; Torgerson et al., 2019 & Woore, 2022).

The aforementioned results confirm that the phonics teaching approach is methodical and effective for pupils with stronger pre-reading skills. Furthermore, the study validated the practices and showed that the delivery of reading instruction to the pupils in the study followed the evidence of reading theory as postulated by other theorists on reading through phonics instruction (Palmer et al., 1985). This finding, therefore, confirms positions advocated by scholars on behavioural reading theories, which assume that reading is learned procedurally. Further, they indicate that learning to read works well with reinforcing and scaffolding routines in the learners by the reading instructors; and that decoding letters, letter blends, and syllable blending leads to early success in the acquisition of reading skills (Freeman, 2004; & Ertmer, 2013).

The pupils who participated in the research were from comparable linguistic, cultural, and geographical backgrounds. Therefore, the pupils had a probable similar schema in these respects. In this case, the cognitive theorists' assumptions that schema aids the acquisition of reading skills (Clark, 2018; Guney & Al, 2012) would have held true and decreased the variance in the reading fluency scores for the pupils under the study. However, this was not the case, as there was marked variation and differentiation in the reading fluency scores. Similar assumptions raised by transactional reading theorists, namely that pupils learn to read through interaction with text and prior experiences (Foster & Rosenblatt, 1998) would have reduced the variance in fluency scores. However, this was also not the case. Therefore, without disputing the usefulness of cognitive and transactional reading theorists, the results indicate that acquiring reading skills at this early stage requires behavioural routines as a basis for learning to read. Once pupils internalise the patterns, they are able to decode words, including nonsense words. Notwithstanding other theories of reading, such as cognitivism and constructivism, which emphasise comprehension, this finding is relevant and useful for comprehension-related reading sub-tasks (Carlson, 1999; Clark, 2018; & Lowenthal & Muth, 2008). Therefore, the behavioural aspect in phonics instruction needs complementing and blending with other reading theories for pupils to master reading and comprehend what they read. This phenomenon is despite the understanding herein that, firstly, phonics require that a pupil can read the word before meaning-making and comprehension processes. This finding explains why those who were able to name the letters, sound the letters, read syllables, and blend syllables into words had an easier time reading words in the paragraphs.

Regardless of the success in reading the words, comprehension remained low on average for fluent students since the test only allowed those who could read the paragraphs to proceed to the reading comprehension test. This finding suggests that the behaviourist phonics reading approach was significantly effective in teaching letter decoding and word reading. However, it is limited in inculcating reading comprehension skills at this level, thus necessitating the application of other advanced reading theories such as constructivism and transactional theories of reading in integrating comprehension skills in the teaching of reading. It further enables the pupils to use prior knowledge, extend the text to non-textbooks and bring more titles to transact with the text in different contexts and make their meanings so that they can apply such strategies in reading comprehension tests. The initial finding supports the earlier position in the literature review that no singular reading theory should dominate a reading approach that informs a reading curriculum (Gourlay, 2003). Instead, strategies and assumptions that are levelled

to the pupils and the independence of teachers and the pupils in instruction and meaning-making should direct applicable theories, not merely targeting fluency as was the case in this study.

In spite of the foregoing, it is evident from the findings of this study that the application of the phonics approach is not the only factor upon which a reading curriculum should be based. Other factors contribute to reading programmes having more sustainable outcomes. For instance, the analysis of variance and further review of the square root of the variance of the residuals (RMSE) was high at 11.4. These results suggest that much as the pre-reading skills explain better oral reading fluency, other factors help pupils learn to read. The pre-reading skills cannot fully explain variation in scores on a test performed in oral reading fluency, thus agreeing with the literature, which shows that other factors such as pupil environment (Afoakwah & Koomson, 2021; Beluska-Turkan, 2019); household factors (Aram, et.al., 2013), and school resource availability (Adamba, 2018; Aas & Brandmo, 2016; Aina 2011; Akech, 2017) have been proven to affect pupils' learning abilities in addition to the reading instruction. These factors earned ground for inclusion in this study to examine further those factors that affect the ability of pupils to learn to read in addition to reading instruction.

4.2. Household factor analysis and respective effects on reading skills acquisition

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) for *z-score* as a response variable to independent predictors mentioned above and available in Table 2, shows that the model is significant ($p = 0$, and $< p = 0.05$). The root MSE (RMSE) is large (0.894951), rightly so, as several factors contribute to the ability of pupils to learn reading, such as pupil and school factors that are not included in this analysis of variance since the primary focus is to nail down factors within the household that explain variation in pupil's abilities to learn reading.

Table 2: ANOVA output on household effect pupil ability to learn reading.

Number of observations = 293			R-squared = 0.2902		
Root MSE = 0.894951			Adj R- squared = 0.1872		
Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Model	83.505047	37	2.22568932	2.82	0.000000
Nursery attendance	1.0669522	2	0.53347609	0.67	0.5146
Meals taken per day	6.1171066	4	1.5292766	1.91	0.1093
language spoken at home	1.760985	2	0.88049249	1.1	0.3347
School attendance	10.753957	5	2.1507915	2.69	0.0219
Reading partners	7.0525126	5	1.4105025	1.76	0.1213
Reading at home	4.8678304	5	0.97356608	1.22	0.3022
Reading practice	6.1752254	1	6.1752254	7.71	0.0059
Reading homework	0.1318358	1	0.13183584	0.16	0.6853
Nutrition intensity	5.0982016	3	1.6994005	2.12	0.0979
Other sources of textbooks	3.4335552	3	1.1445184	1.43	0.2348
Supplementary reading materials	7.5312004	3	2.5104001	3.13	0.0261
Reading places	1.1140395	3	0.37134648	0.46	0.7079
Residual	204.23881	225	0.80093652		
Total	287.74386	292	0.98542418		

The following factors were found statistically significant at 95% confidence interval and explained the variance in the respondent variable: 1) supplementary reading materials (F -statistic = 3.13, $p = 0.0261$), 2) nutrition intensity was marginally significant (F -statistic = 2.12 and $p = 0.079$), 3) reading practice was very significant factor on ability of students to learn reading (F -statistic = 7.71, $p = 0.0059$), 4) times a student attends school was also very significant (F -statistic = 2.69, $p = 0.0129$), and 5) who the pupil read to at home was marginally significant (F -

statistic = 1.76, $p = 0.12$), similarly, for the meals a pupil take in a day (*F-statistic* = 1.91, $p = 0.1093$). This implies that they influence the performance of pupils in the acquisition of reading skills. Therefore, required integration in the reading intervention development and increased level of effort and investment during implementation.

From the assessment, language spoken at home, who the children practiced reading with, whether schools provide reading homework or not, other sources of textbooks, places where a pupil practices reading, and whether one attended nursery or not were found not to predict the performance of students assessed in their acquisition of reading skills. This was largely due to homogeneity in responses than theoretical underpinnings behind these factors, therefore subject to further analysis, perhaps through qualitative inquiry into how these factors may have affected the variation in the ability of pupils assessed to learn reading or level of recorded reading ability.

4.3. Document review on programming decisions made on the Malawi reading intervention based on evidence from household predicting factors

Notably, due to the findings above and from similar studies (Koch, Bobronnikov, Price, Hausdorffk & Prenovitz, 2019), recommendations to focus on the household factors in reading intervention programming have been put forward to change development designs of reading programmes. However, the reading intervention has remained focused on teaching instruction based on the enhanced phonics approach. The investments have followed a similar trend for Malawi and other countries in Africa, such as Ethiopia and Liberia indicating consistent belief in the programming theory aside from evidence that the reading interventions cannot achieve as great on their own, thus require complementary investments in predictors that contribute to the acquisition of reading skills for pupils.

5. Conclusion

It is apparent that the theoretical underpinning of reading interventions in the case of Malawi is solid and follows standardized protocols informing teaching of reading in most countries that are implementing a phonics-based reading approach. However, the investments and level of effort on the reading interventions are not flexible to include other predictors of reading as noted from household assessments conducted herein and previous assessments. While household factors influence reading outcomes for pupils, failure to include investments in these factors in the design and implementation of the reading interventions prevents the sustenance of reading gains and reduces the margin of improvements in the acquisition of reading skills. This study does not place the onus on investments in the complimentary factors within the reading programmes, however calls for the education developers to undertake a systemic investment analysis that allows for simultaneous investments in the household predictors to complement gains achievable for pupils subjected to reading interventions.

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